

1st International Conference Earth Science and Energy

Book of Program

“Renewable Energy for Environmental Sustainability”

Held on 7th - 8th November 2019

at Society M, CitizenM Hotel, Bukit Bintang, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

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1st
ICESE
International Conference Earth Science and Energy

Preface

We are delighted to introduce the *1st International Conference Earth Science And Energy* with theme “Renewable Energy for Environmental Sustainability”. The technical program has brought researchers and practitioners around the world to a good forum for discussing, leveraging and developing all scientific and technological aspects that are relevant to renewable energy. Moreover, it is with a great pleasure to have the keynote and invited speakers of ICESE 2019, Assoc. Prof. Ahmad Fudholi, and Dr. Prantasi Harni Tjahjanti who will share their knowledge and best innovative research findings in energy and earth science. This conference is held by Kresna Nusantara, a company that dedicated to maximize impact of scientific publication, and Relawan Jurnal Indonesia, a non-profit organization in field of scientific publication. Location of this conference is at SocietyM, CitizenM Hotel, Bukit Bintang, Malaysia, on November 7-8, 2019. This conferences was successfully acquire 60 participant from 3 conutries, Indonesia, Malaysia, and Thailand. Thus, all selected papers will be submitted for publication to our publishing partner IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (EES). We hope that the future ICESE 2019 will be as successful and stimulating, as indicated with the contributions presented in this volume.

Kuala Lumpur, November 7, 2019
Conference Chair

Rahmat Hidayat

The Committee of 1st ICESE 2019

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RUNDOWN

Thursday, 7 November, 2019	
07:30-08:00	Registration
08:00-08:25	Opening Ceremony and Welcoming Speech
08:25-09:15	Chairman Report and Paper Selection for Journal Criteria
09:15-11:30	Keynote and Invited Speaker Speech
11:30-12:30	Lunch
12:30-15:30	Oral Presentation
15:30-16:00	Closing and Announcement for the Best presenters and Papers.
Workshop (only for workshop registrant)	
16:00-17:30	How to fund your research in Malaysia
17:30-18:30	Dinner and pray
18:30-21:00	How to get published in Q1 journal. (Highlight your finding, and manage your data)
Friday, 8 November, 2019	
08:00-10:00	Closing Ceremony

PRESENTATION SCHEDULE

ORAL PRESENTATION			
Link for all presentation: https://zenodo.org/communities/icese2019			
ID	Presenter	Title	Time
RJI-1-0061	Albiyan Wanda Syauqi	Design Of Pothole Detector Using Gray Level Co-Occurrence Matrix (Glcm) And Neural Network (Nn)	12:30
RJI-1-0056	Rafidan Maulana Sudibyو	Design Of Coal Handling System For Filling Bunker Using Pid Method In Coal Pltu	12:40
RJI-1-0054	Budi Prasojo	Pipeline Corrosion Protection Simulation Of Cathodic Protection Method Againts Electrochemical Potential Distribution.	12:50
RJI-1-0063	Imam Sutrisno	Vibration Analysis Of Ship-Ruv Structure In Operational Conditions	13:00
RJI-1-0048	Septian Wahyu Saputra	Detection Of Oil And Filter Feasibility In Ship Gearbox With Svm (Support Vector Machine) Method Based On Microcontroller	13:10
RJI-1-110	Arasy Fahrudin	Experimental Study Of Blade Angle Effect On Two-Stage Vertical Shaft Hydrofoil Water Turbines On Power And Efficiency	13:20
RJI-1-111	Prantasi Harmi Tjahjanti	Study Of Crack Connections In Materials Composite Based On Polymer	13:30
RJI-1-0057	Rahmi Karolina	Compressive And Tensile Strength Of Bamboo Species	13:40
RJI-1-0057	Rahmi Karolina	Crack Patterns Analysis On Structural Beam With Slag Cement	13:50
RJI-1-0057	Rahmi Karolina	Shear Behavior Due To Pushover Static Load On Brick Masonry Of Interlock Concrete With The Substitution Of Mount Sinabung Volcanic Ash And With Rebar Reinforcement	14:00
RJI-1-0015	Siti Mutrofin	Application Of A Combination Between Principal Component Analysis And Logistic Regression Based On Support Vector Machine On Educational Data Mining With Overlapping Data Problem	14:10
RJI-1-0019	ELFIZAR	Preserving Riau'S Malay Culture Through Virtual Environment Application	14:20
RJI-1-0021	ELFRIDA RATNAWATI	The Importance Of Railroad Doorstop As A Safety Rule: An Overview Of Responsibilities	14:30
RJI-1-0028	Ida Munfarida	Effects Of Land Use On Sedimentation Rates At Cimanuk Watershed, West Java	14:40
RJI-1-0018	Mukhoirotin	The Investigation Of Il-1 B And Oxytocin Levels Among Teenager With Primary Dysmenorrhea	14:50
RJI-1-0036	Hariyadi	The Influence Of Information Technology And Communication Advancement Especially Smartphone On Muhammadiyah University Of West Sumatera	15:00
RJI-1-108	Jamaaluddin Jamaaluddin	Time Difference Calculation Settings For Very Short Term Electric Load Forecasting Using Interval Type-1 Fuzzy Inference System (It-1 Fis)	15:10
RJI-1-0051	Hanifah Ihsaniyati	Strategy Of Improving The Farmers' Adoption To Temanggung Robusta Coffee'S Geographical Indication Standard	15:20
RJI-1-107	Ribangun Bamban Jakaria	Product Design : Minimize Negative Sustainability Impacts ?	15:30
RJI-1-201	Ignatia Martha Hendrati	Environmental Development and Empowerment from Industrial Impact	15:40
RJI-1-0059	Firman Syarif	Soil Deformation Analysis By Using Plaxis 2D That Cause By Vibration Of Pilling Hammer	15:50
RJI-1-0031	Jarot S Suroso	Cyber Security System With SIEM And Honeypot In Higher Education	16:00

POSTER PRESENTATION

Link for all posters: <https://zenodo.org/communities/icese2019>

ID	Presenter	Title
RJI-1-0062	Uwes Fatoni	Augmented Reality Using Natural Feature Tracking (Nft) Method For Learning Media Of Makharijul Huruf
RJI-1-0062	Uwes Fatoni	Implementation Of K-Means Algorithm In Clustering Al-Quran Verses Based On Pillars Of Islam And Articles Of Faith
RJI-1-100	Yulian Findawati	lot-Based Smart Home Controller Using Nodemcu Lua V3 Microcontroller And Telegram Chat Application
RJI-1-101	Arief Wisaksono	Design And Development Of Information Systems For Rank Building Motorcycle In Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo University
RJI-1-102	Akhmad Ahfas	Otomatis Spray Desinfektan Kandang Ayam Dengan Android Berbasis Arduino Uno
RJI-1-103	Syamsudduha Syahririni	Designing An Internet Of Things Smart Chicken Enclosure
RJI-1-104	Eko Agus Suprayitno	Smart Home Integrated With Internet Of Things (Iot) In The Digital Era Of Industry 4.0
RJI-1-105	Arif Senja Fitriani	Classification Using C4.5 Algorithm In Election Participation Prediction
RJI-1-106	Mochamad Alfian Rosid	Improving Text Preprocessing For Student Complaint Document Classification Using Sastrawi
RJI-1-109	Paramitha Amelia Kusumawardani	Palm Date Increase Adolescents Hemoglobin Levels
RJI-1-0047	Sinto Susilowati	A Challenge Of Inorganic Solid Waste Reduction Practices In Suburban Area
RJI-1-0013	Andrean Eka Lucianto	The Potential Of Solar Panel Implementation Towards Sustainable Affordable Housing Development
RJI-1-0009	Mohammad Galang Merdeka	Estimation Of Oil Recovery For Hydrocarbon Injection Eor Method Using A Newly-Developed Predictive Model